

APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Annotation

This article discusses the development of innovative pedagogical teaching aids and the use of computer training programs, in particular, the use of multimedia tools in the field of lifelong education.

Key words: information technologies, innovative technologies, multimedia technologies, electronic learning tools, distance learning.

In recent years, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to improve the quality of organization of the educational process, special attention has been paid to the use of modern information and innovative pedagogical technologies.

It is no secret that future specialists need to have the skills to constantly improve their knowledge, both in the field of modern information technologies and in the field of their professional activities. Global changes throughout the world are reflected in the education system. The development of this area requires future specialists to continuously engage in self-education. This, in turn, requires intensifying the task of updating the content of university education. At the same time, an intensive approach to the educational process in preparing a modern specialist involves the use of computer training programs, in particular, the use of multimedia tools and elements of distance learning. Their role in the training of a specialist increases significantly based on the types of his professional activities and generalized professional tasks. The pandemic that has affected the whole world has once again emphasized that we must be prepared for all eventualities. And in this regard, multimedia technology acts as an assistant. Here we can talk not only about expanding the scope of the computer in the educational process, but also about the wide possibilities of using text, graphics, video and animation in dialogue mode.

The main features of innovative pedagogical technologies consist of the following:

- the possibility of creating a multi-tiered information environment;
- ensuring reliable and long-term storage of large volumes of information;

- simple forms of processing and use of information;
- interactivity, i.e. the possibility of arbitrary or controlled information management in dialog box mode.

The results expected from the use of innovative pedagogical technologies are ensuring complete and deep perception by students of the information conveyed to them and effectively managing their educational and cognitive activities by including various sensory components of the student in the process of perceiving educational information, transforming educational visibility from static to dynamic. In this regard, it is necessary to pay attention to the advantages of using innovative pedagogical technologies in comparison with traditional technologies and methods. Innovative technologies create the ability to use color graphics, animation, sound, hypertext.

With the help of these technologies, we get the possibility of constant updating, the ability to place interactive web elements, the possibility of non-linear passage of material thanks to many hyperlinks, and hyperlinks with additional literature in electronic libraries or educational sites.

Most often, teachers use multimedia presentations created in MS Power Point for educational purposes. The use of these modern technologies in the education system is in demand. We need to look for new approaches, new solutions to problems. Only then can education keep pace with modern requirements.

Having analyzed the approaches discussed above, we can highlight the main features of the concept of innovative pedagogical technologies:

- educational information is stored and processed electronically;
- presentation of educational information acts as integrated content of text, numerical, audio, graphic, in the form of a three-dimensional model, video, animation;
- clarity is presented in demonstrating the dynamics of the processes being studied;
- web technology for working with data is used, establishing connections between individual terms, text fragments, articles, pictures of the same or different documents;
- educational materials are interactive;
- the learning effect is also based on the multisensory nature of humans.

When considering the impact of innovative pedagogical technologies on students, it can be noted that interaction, firstly, is in the nature of using

pedagogical means as a tool for obtaining knowledge in the disciplines being studied (as a means of self-education).

Secondly, the interaction is in the nature of designing and developing one's own (author's) pedagogical tools, using the capabilities of various application software and programming environments.

The emergence of powerful computer systems and interactive computer programs has become the basis for the intensive development of content and principles for creating electronic textbooks, training programs, their use on mobile devices, tablets for self-education of students, as well as their use in blended and distance learning.

In the blended learning model, handouts for lectures, developed on the basis of electronic notes, are used, focused on the level of knowledge of the audience[1].

In the educational process, you can use a complex of different types of multimedia tools (electronic textbook, video workshop, interactive whiteboard lessons, animation fragments, video lectures), developed by the teaching staff themselves, taking into account the level of training of future specialists.

Despite the large number of advantages, the use of innovative means in the educational process has a number of disadvantages, which the authors point out[3].

There is no general methodology for using innovative tools. Each university has its own developments in the creation and use of multimedia, but there is no single approach for all. It is necessary to systematize this work in order to determine how best to organize the educational process using innovative pedagogical means.

The complexity of creating pedagogical teaching aids is obvious. Not every teacher can create an electronic learning tool with a beautiful and understandable design, and the correct psychological perception of educational material. Creating such tools takes a lot of time.

The use of ready-made designs and templates is not always correct. Some students, as well as teachers, especially in adulthood, do not have the skills to work with electronic learning tools.

Colorful teaching aids distract students due to the abundance of material. Some students do not have the ability to concentrate their attention on the main thing.

For technical sciences, a complex representation of “feedback” from the user. Accordingly, distance learning cannot become the only method of learning due to its limitations for studying these disciplines.

The university does not always have the necessary hardware and software resources. Distance learning places increasingly high demands on the quality of information and communication technologies used.

If the transmission speed on the Internet is insufficient, technical failures occur.

Innovative pedagogical technologies have transformed educational visualization from static to dynamic, that is, it has become possible to track the processes being studied over time. The use of electronic learning tools provides new unique opportunities for developing skills and improving the quality of education.

In conclusion, we note that in scientific and methodological terms, the issue of developing innovative pedagogical teaching aids is developing in the Republic of Uzbekistan. But the creation of these tools requires serious time investment and can be carried out by sufficiently trained specialists.

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